

**KNOWLEDGE OF, ATTITUDES AND PRACTICES TOWARDS HYPERTENSION
AND ITS RISK FACTORS AMONG CLINICAL MEDICAL STUDENTS IN
BINGHAM UNIVERSITY TEACHING HOSPITAL**

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DEDICATION

We dedicate this research first to the Almighty God for His love, amazing grace and mercies that never ends towards us throughout the period of this project, followed by our beloved parents for their unending moral, financial, spiritual support and encouragement, all of which have greatly contributed to our success. Finally, to our supervisor and ourselves, for not giving up halfway on this research.

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ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND

Hypertension is a major health problem in the developed world and also amongst developing countries of which Nigeria is part of. There are many risk factors associated with development of hypertension. They have been classified into modifiable and non-modifiable risk factors. One might wonder why a Knowledge, Attitude Practice (KAP) study on hypertension will be carried out amongst clinical medical students. The purpose of this study is to bring to the cognizance of the world at large the increasing prevalence of hypertension amongst young adults most of whom are university students. This implies the necessity to have a deeper understanding into the Knowledge, attitude and Practices towards hypertension and its risk factors.

AIM: To assess the knowledge of, attitudes and practices towards hypertension and hypertensive risk factors of clinical students in Bingham University Teaching Hospitals.

METHODOLOGY; A cross-sectional descriptive study design was employed. Questionnaires were administered to 283 respondents; Clinical students of Bingham University Teaching Hospital. Data gotten were entered into and analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) and presented using tables and charts.

RESULTS: Majority of the respondents 231(81.9%) were within the 19-24 age group out of 283 respondents.

Majority of the respondents 263(92%) had Good knowledge scores whereas (8%) had wrong knowledge scores. Similarly, a majority 252 (89%) had a Positive attitude while 31(11%) had a negative attitude. 245 (87%) of the respondents were adjudged to have good practices, while 38(13%) were adjudged to have bad practices. The association between knowledge and practices of medical students to the risk factors of hypertension, found out there is a significant positive relationship between good knowledge and good practices, there was no significant positive relationship between good knowledge and bad practices, there was no significant relationship between bad knowledge and good practices. Between bad knowledge and bad practices, there was a negative correlation with -0.267 and a p value which is above the reference point.

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Hypertension is a major health problem in the developed world and also amongst developing countries of which Nigeria is part of. Although it occasionally manifests in an acute aggressive form, high blood pressure is much more often asymptomatic for many years. This insidious condition is sometimes referred to as benign hypertension, but in contrast with its name, it is in fact far from harmless. (1)

According to the World Health Organization, an estimated 1.28 billion adults aged 30–79 years worldwide have hypertension, most (two-thirds) living in low and middle-income countries. An estimated 46% of adults with hypertension are unaware that they have the condition. Less than half of adults (42%) with hypertension are diagnosed and treated. Approximately 1 in 5 adults (21%) with hypertension have it under control. Hypertension is a major cause of premature death worldwide. One of the global targets for non-communicable diseases is to reduce the prevalence of hypertension by 33% between 2010 and 2030. (2) According to a nationwide survey in 2017, the prevalence of hypertension in Nigeria was put at 38.1%. (4) It has been suggested that in recent years, the prevalence of hypertension has largely increased over the last two decades. (5) It is important to note that the prevalence of hypertension amongst Nigerian young adults has also increased in less than 30 years of which a study put the statistic as 6.8%. (4) A key finding from this same study put young adults less than 30 years as having a prevalence of pre-hypertension at 21.3%. (4)

The diagnosis of Hypertension has exerted a high impact on morbidity and mortality rates. In a Cardiovascular Journal of Africa report it was stated that the mortality caused as a result of hypertensive heart disease constituted 0.36% of total deaths. (34) This is indeed quite worrisome.

Adult-onset hypertension is defined and categorized by the Joint National Committee on

Prevention, Detection, Evaluation, and Treatment of High Blood Pressure's Seventh Report (2004) as when the average of two or more diastolic blood pressure readings on at least two following visits is above 90 mm Hg, or when the average of multiple systolic blood pressure readings on two or more subsequent visits is persistently above 140 mm Hg, hypertension is diagnosed. Systolic blood pressure of at least 140 mm Hg and diastolic blood pressure of less than 90 mm Hg is considered isolated systolic hypertension. (3)

Two classes of hypertension have been described. They are Primary hypertension also known as essential hypertension and secondary hypertension. Most adults with hypertension are cases of primary hypertensive. There is no specific cause for primary hypertension as it is thought to be a combination of genetics, diet, lifestyle, and age. Lifestyle factors include smoking, drinking too much alcohol, stress, being overweight, eating too much salt, and not getting enough exercise. Secondary hypertension is a terminology ascribed to hypertension that has identifiable and potentially reversible causes. Only about 5 to 10 percent of hypertension is the secondary type. It is more prevalent in younger people. An estimated 30 percent of those between the ages 18 to 40 with hypertension have secondary hypertension. (4)

There are many risk factors associated with development of hypertension. They have been classified into modifiable and non-modifiable risk factors. Example of non-modifiable risk factors include excessive salt consumption, a diet high in saturated fat and trans fats, low intake of fruits and vegetables, physical inactivity, consumption of tobacco and alcohol, and being overweight or obese. Non-modifiable risk factors include family history of hypertension, age over 65 years and co-existing diseases such as diabetes or kidney disease. (2)

Hypertension is usually asymptomatic except in the case of malignant hypertension. (6) Very high blood pressures can become symptomatic causing headaches, blurred vision, chest pain, dizziness, difficulty breathing, nausea, vomiting, anxiety, confusion, buzzing

in the ears, nosebleeds, abnormal heart rhythm. (2) Uncontrolled hypertension exerts multi-systemic effects. It could affect the cardiovascular system causing left ventricular hypertrophy, congestive heart failure, ischemic heart disease, atherosclerosis, and arrhythmias. Strokes and hypertensive encephalopathy are the major Central Nervous system manifestations of uncontrolled hypertension. Uncontrolled hypertension could also result in hypertensive nephropathy and retinopathy affecting the kidneys and the eyes respectively. Malignant hypertension and accelerated hypertension are also complications resulting from poor control of hypertension. (6)

One might wonder why a Knowledge, Attitude Practice (KAP) study on hypertension will be carried out amongst clinical medical students. The purpose of this study is to bring to the cognizance of the world at large the increasing prevalence of hypertension amongst young adults most of whom are university students. This implies the necessity to have a deeper understanding into the Knowledge, attitude and Practices towards hypertension and its risk factors. Clinical medical students are at a critical stage in their educational attainment where an appropriate understanding of hypertension and its risk factors is pertinent in saving the lives of multitudes when they become full-fledged healthcare providers. The aim of this study is to address knowledge gaps, prevailing attitudes, and practices amongst these medical students. As the study population comprises future healthcare professionals, it is imperative that the healer should not be in a position to need healing from illnesses like hypertension. This can only be achieved if proper knowledge, attitude and practices towards hypertension are adopted by these clinical students.

Good Knowledge is the bedrock of effective healthcare practices. These clinical students must have a good grasp and understanding of hypertension and its risk factors. Also, epidemiology, pathophysiology, diagnostic criteria, treatment strategies are important in evaluating how well knowledgeable these students are regarding the topic of this discourse. Assessing their knowledge of modifiable and non-modifiable risk factors of hypertension will provide insights into mitigating knowledge gaps.

Assessing the attitudes of these clinical students to avoidance of hypertension and its risk factors will prove helpful not only in correcting poor attitudes but ultimately in appropriate and optimal patient care. Medical students ultimately become doctors but reports have it that they display nonchalant attitudes towards having healthy living practices. (10)

Active practices carried out by medical students in order to maintain healthy status toward avoiding hypertension need to be evaluated. According to a study of undergraduate medical students by Harsha Choudary et al, it was stated that only 47% did adequate exercises. It also stated that 3.9% of these same students consumed junk food every day. (9) There are few Nigerian literatures to back or counter claims such as these hence, the purpose of this study. Having healthy practices for curbing hypertension will not only prove helpful to the medical student, but the populace that will be served by these future healthcare professionals.

1.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

In Nigeria, hypertension is a prevalent health condition that affects approximately 38.1% of the its population. (4) Despite this rising rate, there are still knowledge gaps and misconceptions surrounding hypertension among the general population and medical students. Studies suggest that many Nigerians have limited knowledge of hypertension, its symptoms, causes, risk factors, diagnosis, and management. This may be due to a lack of awareness, limited access to health care, cultural beliefs and practices and socioeconomic factors such as poverty. (8)

Additionally, among some medical students, some causes of knowledge gaps include inadequate training and education on hypertension during medical school and continuing education programs, insufficient research and data on hypertension in Nigeria, limited funding for some medical schools and limitation to lecturers and lack familiarity with newer diagnostic techniques and treatment guidelines. These gaps in knowledge and

misconceptions could have negative consequences for the future management and treatment of hypertension which would lead to an increased risk of complications and mortality or a failure to diagnose the condition early leading to uncontrolled hypertension which can cause damage to heart, kidneys and brain. overall failure to address the knowledge gaps, negative attitudes and bad practices among medical students could have significant public health implications and increase the burden of hypertension in Nigeria. Although there have been efforts to increase awareness and knowledge of hypertension in Nigeria, ongoing education and training are necessary to ensure that medical students and healthcare providers have up-to-date knowledge of hypertension and its management.

Attitudes towards hypertension, including its management and treatment, can vary depending on cultural and societal factors. In general, hypertension is a common topic in medical education and medical students are generally taught the importance of identifying and managing high blood pressure in patients. However, like the general population, some do not prioritize their own health and may not consistently monitor their blood pressure or take steps to manage it if it is high. Additionally, medical students may face unique challenges that can affect their health, such as long hours, high stress, and irregular work schedules, which may make it more difficult to manage their blood pressure. This was seen in a study carried out by Harsha Choudary in which 47% of the study population of medical students did adequate physical activity, and walking was the commonest physical activity. (9) Overall, the attitudes of medical students towards their own hypertension management may vary depending on individual factors and circumstances.

However, there are still some misconceptions and stigmas associated with hypertension. For example, some people may believe that hypertension only affects older individuals or those who are overweight, when in fact it can affect anyone regardless of age or body type, this study will help us know if the medical students of BHUTH have the right information.

Medical students are generally taught to follow evidence-based guidelines for the management of hypertension, which may include lifestyle modifications [such as regular exercise, healthy diet, and stress reduction], as well as medications if necessary. As health care professionals, medical students are also typically aware of the importance of regular blood pressure monitoring and may check their own pressure periodically. However, like the general population, medical students may not follow these practices consistently, especially if they are too busy with school work and other commitments.

1.3 JUSTIFICATION

The importance of this topic cannot be stressed enough. Despite being clinical medical students, there is a wanton disregard for healthy living practices amongst students (10). Inherently, this would imply that they will have a greater risk of developing hypertension compared to the general public. This was revealed in an AHA Hypertension Scientific Session. The study presented concluded that medical students were at a 2.4 times greater risk of developing Stage 2 hypertension. (11) This is not meant to be so because as these clinical students are healthcare workers in training. This study is meant to bring to the consciousness of clinical students the need to take care of themselves health-wise as they will soon be in positions to render healthcare advice to their patients. Healthcare workers are exposed to a lot of occupational risk factors which are stress related such as high workload, small breaks, insomnia during night shifts and dietary irregularities. (12) Hence, there is a rising prevalence of hypertension amongst hospital employees such as doctors, nurses and invariably medical students.

Another reason to justify this study is the paucity of literature concerning this topic amongst our study population and surrounding Jos environment. This project is meant to shed more light on rising rates of Hypertension amongst university students who are usually youths. As cardiovascular diseases constitute a rising concern, this research study seeks to provide research results data and results that will prove useful for future studies regarding this topic. The results from this study can form the bedrock of studies providing insight into high stress occupations and a better knowledge of the connection between

stress, lifestyle choices and hypertension.

Assessing the Knowledge, Attitude and Practices of these medical students will identify gaps and deficiencies in their knowledge base and help in reforming medical education in order to address these shortcomings. By addressing this, future health professionals i.e., medical students will be effectively equipped in providing pinpoint diagnoses and treatment plans for hypertensive patients. I would dare say that patients will be the greatest benefactors of healthcare administered by medical students with good Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice study. Hence, patient outcomes will be improved alongside highly qualitative healthcare quality.

Lastly, a concise evaluation of medical students' attitudes and practices will prove pertinent in developing appropriate recommendations to mitigate the rising prevalence of hypertension amongst medical students as a global health concern.

1.4. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This project seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of Knowledge of clinical students in BhUTH on hypertension and its risk factors?
2. What is the Attitude of clinical students in BhUTH towards hypertension and its risk factors?
3. What are the Common practices of clinical students in BhUTH towards avoidance of hypertensive risk factors?
4. What is the association between Clinical students' knowledge of hypertension and its risk factors and Practice towards avoidance of these risk factors?

1.5. OBJECTIVES

General Objectives

To assess the knowledge, attitude and practices of clinical students in BhUTH towards Hypertension and hypertensive risk factors.

Specific Objectives

1. To evaluate the level of knowledge of hypertension and hypertensive risk factors among clinical medical students.
2. To assess the attitudes of clinical medical students towards avoidance of hypertension and hypertensive risk factors.
3. To identify common practices that contribute to the avoidance of hypertension and hypertensive risk factors among medical students.
4. To find out the association between Clinical students' knowledge of hypertension and its risk factors and Practice towards avoidance of these risk factors

1.6 OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS

Knowledge

It refers to the response to the items on hypertension as measured by knowledge questionnaire and expressed in terms of knowledge score i.e. high, moderate or poor.

Attitude

Attitude refers to how people interact in a certain way to certain situations, to see and interpret events according to certain predispositions or to organize opinions into coherent and interrelated structures.

Practice

It refers to the activities or health change in behavior that is actually accepted and followed by hypertensive patients as a part of life. (35)

BhUTH

Bingham University Teaching Hospital

KAP questions tend to reveal not only characteristic traits in knowledge, attitude, and behaviors about health but also the idea that each person has of the disease. These factors are often the source of misunderstandings. The obstacle to change may be lack of knowledge. Recent reports have suggested that hypertension knowledge is related to blood pressure control. The importance of hypertension awareness and knowledge and

the potential impact of blood pressure education programs have been reported on recently. Although the outcome of a knowledge, attitude and practice study seems simple, the results of the study can have a huge impact on the local community. As the KAP study explores what is known and what is done in relation to a health care-related objective which is about hypertension in this study, the results will reveal the baseline information of the community and may reveal the misconceptions or misbehaviors in relation to practice of hypertension. It is very important to identify these facts as these directly influence the future health care-related interventions. Moreover, results of the knowledge, attitude and practices study establish reference values on various health care parameters for use in future assessments. Also, aspects assessed by the KAP study are not uniform to the entire communities. Therefore, results of the KAP study derived based on Western data cannot be applied to our local community. In summary, it is justifiable to conduct a study on assessment of knowledge, attitude, and practice in relation to hypertension in a local community as this will reveal important unknown data on hypertension to guide future research studies and health-related interventions. (7)

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

Hypertension, or high blood pressure, is a common disease that manifests as elevated systemic arterial pressures. Hypertension is most often asymptomatic and is found incidentally as part of a routine physical examination or during triage for an unrelated medical encounter.

While medical school is known to cause mental and physical strain on medical students, a recent study presented at the American Heart Association's Hypertension 2019 Scientific Session (14) examined how medical school can impact their health. Results of the study, which involved 213 medical students, revealed just 36.6% of first- and second-year medical students had normal blood pressure levels while 29.1% had stage 1 hypertension and 17.8% had stage 2 hypertension. While this is a small study, it is interesting. As one of the most common and dangerous risk factors for heart disease and stroke, all people, even those who are young and believed to be in good health, should have their blood pressure checked routinely. Of the 213 students included in the study 49.8% were male and the mean age of the cohort was 25.8 years — investigators noted the overall age range of participants was 21 to 37 years old. Students completed a survey that assessed age, gender, diet, alcohol consumption, diet, aerobic exercise, mental health, social support, and past medical history. Blood pressure was measured using Omron BP710N sphygmomanometers and waist circumference was measured around the umbilicus. Upon analysis, 36.6% (78/213) of students were considered normotensive, 16.4% (35/213) had prehypertension, 29.1% had stage 1 hypertension, and 17.8% (38/213) had stage 2 hypertension. Investigators noted the regression model was significant and explained 51.6% of the variance in hypertension — additionally, it correctly classified 57.4% of cases.

Exercise, anxiety, and diet were insignificant factors in the regression model while gender, waist circumference, and amount of sleep were considered significant. Male students were 13.26 times more likely ($P < 0.001$) to develop hypertension than female students. A 1-inch increase in waist circumference was associated with an 11% increase in developing stage 2 hypertension ($P < 0.001$).

Based on results of the study, investigators concluded medical students were at a 2.4 times greater risk of developing stage 2 hypertension.

"Elevated blood pressure should not be something that we only associate with being older," said lead investigator Jacek Bednarz, Jr., a third-year medical student at Lincoln Memorial University. "Young people lack awareness about their own blood pressure. Getting your blood pressure regularly checked is a simple way to protect one's health."

2.2 KNOWLEDGE OF HYPERTENSION AND HYPERTENSIVE RISK FACTORS

A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted by Sahni Gurpreet et al on "Knowledge and awareness of Hypertension among Medical Students and Junior Doctors at Government Medical College and Rajindra Hospital Patiala, Punjab" from Jan. 2017 to Feb. 2017 at GMC & RH Patiala on 450 participants. The study consisted of a structured, questionnaire focusing on diagnostic issues of hypertension, Pharmacological treatment of hypertension, therapeutic strategies regarding hypertension and target BP. The result of the study undoubtedly indicated an inadequate level of awareness of diagnosis, work up and treatment of arterial hypertension among our participants at Government Medical College Patiala and Rajindra Hospital Patiala. Of the total participants, 333 knew the cut off level of blood pressure to define hypertension in an otherwise healthy person. Our study showed that overall, 157 subjects possessed adequate knowledge of hypertension. This was higher among residents 57, followed by medical students 9 and interns 8. Residents tend to have better knowledge regarding the treatment as 62.5% responded with the correct answers regarding treatment questions while only 30% of the interns and 7.5% of the final year medical students were aware of

treatment options for hypertension in WHO/ISH QUESTIONNAIRE. The study showed that residents tend to have better knowledge regarding the treatment (6 out of 10 questions are clinical aspects of hypertension) as 62.5% responded with the correct answers about treatment questions while only 30% of the interns and 7.5% of the final year medical students were aware of treatment options for hypertension. Of the total participants, 333 knew the cut off level of blood pressure to define hypertension in an otherwise healthy person. (15)

Another cross-sectional study was carried out by F. E. Omotoye and R. A. Sanusi in 2018 on "Awareness of hypertension and factors associated with uncontrolled hypertension among Nigerian adults" a community-based study in six local government areas in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Random sampling method was used to select participants and data collection was by researcher-administered questionnaire. A total of 1590 respondents (20–70 years) with a mean age of 43.9 ± 16.4 years participated in the study. Participants diagnosed as hypertensive were 524. Among the hypertensive, 214 (40.8%) were aware of their Hypertension status. Awareness was higher in females 163 (31.1%) than in males 51 (9.7%), increased with age and decreased with higher educational status.

Hypertension awareness was low in the study area. Uncontrolled Hypertension was associated with risk factors of Hypertension and lifestyle and was more prominent in the female gender. (16)

A descriptive cross-sectional was conducted by Pugie Tawanda ChimberengwaI and Mergan Naidoo, on behalf of the cooperative inquiry group Discipline of Public Health Medicine, School of Nursing and Public Health, University of KwaZulu-Natal, Durban, South Africa in 2019. The study was on "Knowledge, attitudes and practices related to hypertension among residents of a disadvantaged rural community; Matebele land in southern Zimbabwe. 304 respondents were enrolled into the study (mean age, 59 years), and a majority were women (65.4%). Knowledge on hypertension was poor, with 64.8% of respondents stating that stress was its main cause, 85.9% stated that palpitations were

a symptom of hypertension and 59.8% of respondents added salt on the table. The more education respondents had received, the more likely they were knowledgeable about hypertension. Poor knowledge was associated with a lack of education and with strong beliefs in herbal and traditional medicines in the community, which influenced attitudes and practices on hypertension. Dietary risk factors were linked to poor knowledge. (17)

This cross-sectional survey was conducted by Mohammed Hisam, Asma Nour and Shayoub M in 2018 on "Assessment of Knowledge about Hypertension among students of the first year in medical colleges, in International University of Africa (IUA)". The age of participants was found 20 years 95 (41%), while the gender was found as following male 90 (39%) and 140 (61%) females, none of the participants is a smoker, while only 44(19%) have no family history of hypertension. The overall knowledge of students was found to be 62.97%. (18)

A descriptive cross-sectional study was accomplished by Mukhtiar Baig et al, at Jeddah, Saudi Arabia, in 2014 titled "Prevalence of obesity and hypertension among University students' and their knowledge and attitude towards risk factors of Cardiovascular Disease (CVD) in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia". The aim of the study was to investigate the prevalence of obesity and hypertension among university students. They recommended that a large scale awareness program should be initiated from health ministry on the electronic and print media. (22)

Sahni Gurpreet et al carried out a descriptive cross-sectional study titled "Knowledge and awareness of Hypertension among Medical Students and Junior Doctors at Government Medical College and Rajindra Hospital Patiala, Punjab". This was conducted from Jan 2017 to Feb 2017 at GMC & RH Patiala on 450 participants. The purpose of this research study was to evaluate the knowledge about hypertension among medical students, interns and residents working in GMC & RH Patiala. Recommendation of evidence-based curriculum was suggested to likely plug the gap in deficient knowledge of our future

physicians. Therefore, further efforts are required to intensify information strategies for improving professional education and training aimed achieving therapeutic goals. (15)

2.3 ATTITUDE TOWARDS AVOIDANCE OF HYPERTENSION AND HYPERTENSIVE RISK FACTORS

A cross sectional descriptive study was done in Kinodoni municipal on university students which included some medical students towards risk factors of hypertension and the result showed that from the study it was found that 66.8% of the study population had knowledge of hypertension but only 19.75% had knowledge of the risk factors for hypertension. Slightly more than half of the study population reported to be doing physical exercises but the number of men (70.6%) exercising was found to be more than twice that of women (29.94%) The number of people who used to smoke was 30 (9.54%). Out of 30 people only 2 (6.67%) women used to smoke. The number of people who used to drink alcohol was 94 (29.56%) but the number of men 62 (65.96%) was approaching twice that of women 32 (34.04%). This shows that both men and women are predisposed to risk factors for hypertension. The difference is in the types of risk factors as it was seen above that men drink and smoke more compared to women but again males do physical exercises more compared to females. (19) This study clearly shows that though people have good knowledge, they have a negative attitude towards hypertension which could be detrimental in the long run

A cross sectional study was carried out on a randomly selected sample of 340 medical students of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife. The results showed that 75.0% had normal nutritional status, 10.0% were underweight and the prevalence of obesity was 1.2%. A significant association was noted between the BMI categories and nutritional knowledge ($p < 0.05$). The majority of the students had normal nutritional status and average nutritional scores. The food habit involving regular meal skipping was reported.[2] Though their medical students had good knowledge of nutrition, they didn't put in practice their knowledge, some studies also show due to the work load of medical

students, they have less time to prepare good meals and end up eating junk foods which could lead to high cholesterol and in the long run predispose them to hypertension and other Cardiovascular disease. (20)

It is a cross-sectional descriptive study conducted among undergraduate medical students of Guntur district, Andhra Pradesh. In the study, 336 students participated. The results were analyzed and they are as follows: In the present study knowledge regarding hypertension and its associated risk factors is found to be increasing as years of study is increasing. Positive attitude towards risk factors for hypertension is found to be maximum (99.3%) among final years in the present study more than 90% of the study population are including fruits in their diet. The habit of junk food eating is found to be around 50%. Only 47% of the study population are doing adequate physical exercise and walking is found to be the common physical activity. Harmful habits like tobacco use, alcohol intake and high salt intake is found to be very low in the present Study. Knowledge and attitude of medical students of various semesters are good towards risk factors of hypertension but the warning signs are about half of study participants are not doing regular physical exercise & consuming junk food & some of them are having habits of alcohol, smoking which are modifiable risk factors that leads to hypertension at very early age. (21)

After obtaining the institutional ethical clearance and permission from the authorities, a cross-sectional survey was conducted for 100 medical students at a health university in western Maharashtra, India. The participants were enrolled for the study by convenience sampling after they were informed about the purpose of the study and the method of completing the questionnaire. A total of 130 students comprising 74 girls and 56 boys from the health university participated in the study. All the students were staying in the hostel of the university. Eighty-three (68%) responders out of 130 said that they had breakfast daily. However, only 13 participants (10%) said that they had a fruit daily in our study. Daily consumption of fruits and vegetables was only 1–2 portions for 98 (75%) of the participating students. Out of 130 students studied regarding snacks preference,

fried snacks were the most popular with 51 (39%) students, followed by various bakery items by 30 students. Only 9 (7%) students preferred salads and soups for snacking.[31] These practices would have a negative effect on their health in the long run and could predispose them to hypertension in future.

These above observations resemble that of a study conducted by Faculty of Medicine, Mansoura University, Egypt which showed that two-thirds of the 908 medical students included in the study consumed fast food regularly. These facts are alarming as the high prevalence of fast/junk food preference and consumption by future health-care practitioners poses a serious health concern. [32] The study showed obesity in 2.3% of the study population. Similar value of 6.1% obese female medical students as seen in the study by Garipağaoğlu *et al.* on 2012.

2.4 PRACTICES THAT CONTRIBUTE TO AVOIDANCE OF HYPERTENSION AND HYPERTENSIVE RISK FACTORS

A descriptive cross-sectional study was accomplished by Mukhtiar Baig et al, at Jeddah, Saudi Arabia, in 2014. A total of 610 male students were selected for the study. The objective of the study was to investigate the prevalence of obesity and hypertension among university students' and their knowledge and attitude towards risk factors of cardiovascular disease (CVD) in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia. The study observed suboptimal practicing (20%) among the participants. 19.7% of the participants exercised more than 20 minutes 3days/week, 25.4% played outdoor games daily/thrice in a week, 3.4% ate outside home, 32.5% used more than 3 teaspoon salt/day, 13.0% avoided fatty foods, 11.3% maintained normal weight, 6.4% tried to reduce stress, 13.4% avoided smoking, 49.8% visited doctor for advice, 31% ate fish thrice/week, 17.5% gained knowledge about CVD through mass media or electronic, 20.3% tried to prevent CVD (22)

Takele Tadesse et al conducted an Institution-based cross-sectional study was conducted among randomly selected college students in Gondar, Ethiopia in December 2012. This study measured the prevalence of hypertension and associated factors among university students in Gondar, Ethiopia. A total of 610 college students were screened for

hypertension. 2.6% smoked cigarettes. 40.0% smoked daily. 38% consumed an alcoholic drink within the past 12 months. 7.1% frequently consumed alcohol during the past 12 months. (23)

Mlunde Linda et al in 2007 carried out a cross sectional descriptive study with a total of 319 people were interviewed. The aim of this study was to assess the people's knowledge, attitudes and practices towards risk factors for hypertension in Kinondoni Municipality. People who reported to be doing physical exercises were 52.35%, smoking 9.54% and drinking alcohol 29.56%. 73.05% of the study population reportedly did physical exercises so as to be physically fit. 23.35% engaged in physical exercising because they liked it. 76.67% smoked because they liked it. 77.66% drank alcohol because they liked it. (19)

A 2022 study titled Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice Toward Hypertension Among Hypertensive Patients Residing in Lebanon carried out by Marc Machaalani et al involved 342 hypertensive patients. This study aimed to determine HTN KAP among hypertensive patients residing in Lebanon. 57.0% of HTN patients displayed poor knowledge while. 21.1% displayed fair knowledge implying "Limited" knowledge. Only 21.93% of HTN patients showed an "Adequate" Practice level. (24)

Dan Gong et al performed a cross-sectional survey on "Hypertension-Related Knowledge, Attitudes, and Behaviors among Community-Dwellers at Risk for High Blood Pressure in Shanghai, China" in 2017. The aim of this study was to investigate Knowledge, Attitude and Behaviours regarding hypertension prevention. 72.5% did not smoke. 72.5% did not drink alcohol. 44.8% controlled salt intake. 50.2% controlled oil intake. 41.7% adequately consumed fresh fruit. 59.2% appropriately consumed meat. 93.6% adequately consumed fresh vegetable. 38.1% balanced meat and vegetable intake. 48.8% controlled their body weight. 30.9% performed frequent physical activity. 89.4% had low stress from work and life. 84.9% were Rarely nervous or panic. 76.9% monitored

BP regularly. (25)

Jennifer Anyanti et al conducted a descriptive cross-sectional study titled “Assessment of the level of knowledge, awareness and management of hypertension and diabetes among adults in Imo and Kaduna states, Nigeria: a cross-sectional study” in 2020. This study was designed to assess levels of awareness, knowledge, attitude and practices relating to hypertension and diabetes among 824 adults aged 35 years resident in selected communities in Imo and Kaduna states, Nigeria. 36.8% currently take alcohol. 8.0% currently smoke. 54.6% minimized salt intake in the prevention/control of hypertension. 32.5% reduced intake of fatty foods. 26.0% avoided excessive intake of alcohol. 13.5% avoided smoking. 57.5% performed regular exercise. 4.2% avoided anxiety. 0.8% prayed. 6.4% didn't know any preventive practice. (26)

2.5 ASSOCIATION BETWEEN KNOWLEDGE OF AND PRACTICES TO CURB HYPERTENSION AND ITS RISK FACTORS

It is important to establish whether there is an association between knowledge of hypertension and practices that contribute to the avoidance of this disease.

In a cross sectional descriptive study conducted by Fakhri Sabouhi et al in Iran enlisting 234 participants, whose aim was to assess the “Awareness, knowledge, and practice of hypertensive patients and its relation to demographic data”. It was stated in results obtained that there was no significant relationship between knowledge and practice. (34)

Another study carried out by Mukhiar Baig in 2014, aimed to identify the “Prevalence of obesity and hypertension among university students’ and their knowledge and attitude towards risk factors of CVD established an association between knowledge of and practices regarding avoidance of hypertensive risk factors. It showed that students with poor knowledge were likely to exhibit poor avoidance practices. (22)

CHAPTER 3

METHODOLOGY

3.1 STUDY AREA

Plateau State, our study area is the twelfth largest state of Nigeria, and is roughly located in the center of the country. It is geographically unique in Nigeria because its boundaries totally surround the Jos Plateau, having the Jos Plateau totally in its central and northern parts. Its capital is Jos. Plateau State is celebrated as "The Home of Peace and Tourism". Plateau State gets its name from the Jos Plateau. It has a population of around 3.5 million people. The study area is located in Jos north Local Government, it has an area of 291km square and a population of 429,300 at the 2006 census. (29)

3.2 STUDY LOCATION

This study was carried out at Bingham University Jos Campus, Jos, Plateau State, Nigeria. Bingham University is a Private University owned by Evangelical Church Winning All (ECWA) and was established in 2005. The University has 2 campuses; the main campus located in New Karu, Nasarawa state and the Jos Campus, where the College of Medicine and Health Science is located, in Bingham University Teaching Hospital Jos, Plateau State. The College of Health Science is where the clinical medical students of Bingham University carry out their academic activities while the academic activities of all other students are carried out in the main campus.

3.3 STUDY POPULATION

The study population comprised of clinical medical students of BhUTH (400-600 level) with a population of 552 medical students.

3.4 STUDY DESIGN:

This was a cross-sectional descriptive study to determine the knowledge, attitude and practices of clinical students in BhUTH towards Hypertension and hypertensive risk factors.

Inclusion criteria:

Medical students of Bingham University from 400-600 level.

Those who give consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion criteria:

Those who are either not students or not clinical students of Bingham University.

Students who did not give their consent to participate in the study.

3.5 STUDY DURATION:

The duration of this study was about 3 months

3.6 SAMPLE SIZE DETERMINATION:

The minimum sample size for this study was determined using Taro Yamane's formula:

$n = N/[1 + N(e)^2]$, where:

n = the sample size

N = population under study

e = the margin of error (which can be 0.10, 0.05 or 0.01)

Population under study= 552

The margin of error 0.05

$n = 552/[1 + 552(0.05)^2] = 231.7$ approximately 232

Attrition of 10% = $232/100 \times 10 = 23.2$ approximately 23

Attrition of 10% = 23

Sample size = n + 10% of attrition

Therefore, $232 + 23 = 255$

Hence, the minimum sample size is 255

3.7 SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

A Multi-stage sampling technique was adopted as follows:

Stage 1 – A particular number of students were selected from each class.

Out of the 552 students distributed in 5 classes, there were 124 students in 2015/2016, 85 students in 2016/2017, 132 students in 2017/2018 set, 79 students in 2018/2019 set and 132 students in 2019/2020 set.

There was proportional allocation based on size of the class using the formula:

Proportion (p) = Number of Students in each class/Total Number of Students in BhUTH

(t) (n) X Sample Size

a) 2015/2016 – number in class = 124, $124/552 \times 255 = 57$

b) 2016/2017 – number in class = 85, $85/552 \times 255 = 39$

c) 2017/2018 – number in class = 132, $132/552 \times 255 = 61$

d) 2018/2019 – number in class =79, $79/552 \times 255 = 36$

e) 2019/2020 – number in class =132, $123/552 \times 255 = 61$

Stage 2 – Selection was based on Gender. Both genders were proportionally represented because the population of females is higher than that of males.

Using the formula: number of a gender in the class (n)/ Total number of students in the class X proportion of sample.

a) For2015/2016 males =63 and females = 61

proportion of male samples will be $(63/124) \times 57 = 29$ males

proportion of female samples will be $(61/124) \times 57= 28$ females

b) For 2016/2017, males = 39 and females = 46

Proportion of male samples will be $(39/85) \times 39= 18$ males

Proportion of female samples will be $(46/85) \times 39 = 21$ females

c) For the 2017/2018, males = 45 and females = 87

Proportion of male samples will be $(45/132) \times 61 = 21$ males

Proportion of female samples will be $(87/132) \times 61 = 40$ females

d) For the 2018/2019, males =22 and females = 57

Proportion of male samples will be $(22/79) \times 36 = 10$ males

Proportion of female samples will be $(57/79) \times 36 = 26$ females

e) For the 2019/2020, males = 53 and females = 79

Proportion of male samples will be $(53/132) \times 61 = 25$ males

Proportion of female samples will be $(79/132) \times 61 = 37$ females

Total number of males = 103

Total number of females = 152

Simple Random Sampling was applied to this study using the balloting technique to get the sample.

3.8 DATA COLLECTION

Data was collected using a properly structured, self-administered on-line questionnaire developed by researchers. The questionnaire was made up of five sections which included the following:

Section A: Consent

Section B: Socio-demographic information

Section C: Questions to assess the level of Knowledge of clinical students on hypertension and its risk factors

Section D: Questions on the attitudes of clinical students towards hypertension and its risk factors

Section E: Questions on the practice of clinical students towards avoidance of hypertensive risk factors

3.9 DATA ANALYSIS

Analysis of data collected was done using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), the result was analyzed into tables and charts. The creation of the charts, tables and figures was done using Microsoft Office Excel and determination of correlation coefficient was determined using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS).

Knowledge of hypertension & hypertensive risk factors was assessed by questions which were of the TRUE/FALSE type. Each variable was awarded a score of 1 for correct answers and 0 for wrong answers. In the case of optimal blood pressure of hypertensives, a score of 1 mark was awarded to 130/80, 0 marks 120/80, -1 90/60, -2 for 160/100. The minimum score was 0 and the maximum score was 39. Using the cutoff of 77%,

respondent who scored above this threshold (greater or equal 30) were considered to have good knowledge and those below this threshold (less than 30) were considered to have poor knowledge of Hypertension and its risk factors

Attitudes towards avoidance of hypertension and hypertensive risk factors was assessed using the 5-point Likert scale. The most correct variable was awarded a score of 5, while the next correct answer was awarded a score of 4, the neutral variable was awarded a score of 3. A wrong answer was awarded a score of 2. The most wrong answer was awarded the score of 1. Maximum score in this section was 80 while the minimum was 0. The cut off mark was at 80% meaning people that got below 64 marks were awarded bad attitudes and 64 marks and above were adjudged to have good attitudes.

In the assessment of practices that contribute to avoidance of hypertension and hypertensive risk factors. 3 marks were awarded for the most correct answer, 2 marks were awarded for a correct answer and 0 marks were awarded for a wrong answer. The cut off was 67%- 16 marks. Implying that persons with less than 16 marks were adjudged to exhibit Bad practices while persons with 16 marks and above were awarded Good practices

3.10 ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

This was an information collection study with no invasion of the human body and thus no untoward physical harm to the participants. Ethical clearance was obtained from Bingham University Teaching Hospital Ethical Committee for the study. Permission was sought from the Office of the Chief Medical Director through the Office of the Chairman, Medical Advisory Committee, for permission for the study among the staff of the hospital. There was a separate *“Participant’s Consent and Information”* form that outlined the information on the research and solicitation of participant’s consent. On this, each participant was required to voluntarily affirm his/her consent and willingness to participate at participant level; with the assurance of non-repercussions should he/she

wish to opt out. Each participant will be requested to sign upon consent and detached off to ensure the privacy of their identities, as only this document *“Participant’s Consent and Information”* form contains the identity of each consenting participant and will not be reflected in the questionnaire. To link questionnaire to database, each questionnaire will be appended a number serving as the code and linked to a master database (containing the names of the participants) that will remain in the custody of only the researcher for ease of cross-checking and reverting to any participant should further clarification based on response provided in the questionnaire. Collected questionnaire and collated data are to be domiciled in the protective custody of the principal researcher (team leader) to avoid needless spread of participants’ information with guided access only to research team. Database will be kept strictly with the researching team and will not be made available or known to anyone outside the team.

The essential monitoring plan will be in line with supervisor’s periodic review and meeting with research team members. This plan itemizes time for administration of questionnaire, data analysis and documentation (report writing) and submission.

At the end of the research and final approval of report, questionnaires were discarded through appropriate means that prevented public access to them and database protected.

At the conclusion of the assessment of the study outcome, and with no further need for database, it will be deleted immediately to permanently prevent access any further.

3.11. STUDY LIMITATIONS

1. There is a probability that we might encounter low questionnaire response from these clinical medical students due to busy schedules borne out of class and ward activities.
2. Sample size may be too small to generalize the findings in the larger population of clinical medical students.

CHAPTER 4

RESULTS

This chapter shows the results from 283 respondents on “Knowledge of, attitude and practices towards hypertension and its risk factors”

4.1 Sociodemographic Data

Table 1.1: Ages of Respondents

AGES	Frequency	(%)
19	6	2.1
20	29	10.2
21	36	12.7
22	54	19.0
23	62	21.9
24	45	15.9
25	19	6.7
26	9	3.2
27	5	1.8
28	11	3.9
29	3	1.1
30	3	1.1
36	1	0.4
TOTAL	283	100

Table 1.0 above shows the ages of the respondents. Students aged 19 had a frequency of 6 (2.1%), students aged 20 had a frequency of 21(10.2%) and students aged 21 had a

frequency of 36 (12.7%), students aged 22 had a frequency of 54(19%) ,students aged 23 had a frequency of 62 (21.9 %), students aged 24 had a frequency of 45(15.9%) , students aged 25 had a frequency of 19(6.7%), students aged 26 had a frequency of 9 (3.2%), students aged 27 had a frequency of 5 (1.8%), students aged 28 had a frequency of 11(3.9%), students aged 29 had a frequency of 3(1.1%), students aged 30 had a frequency of 3(1.1%) and students aged 36 had a frequency of 1(0.4%).

Table: 1.2 Sex

	2015/2016	2016/2017	2017/2018	2018/2019	2019/2020	Frequency(%)
Female	33	26	41	32	37	169(59.7)
Male	32	20	24	13	25	114(40.3)
TOTAL	65	46	65	45	62	283(100)

Table 1.2 shows that 169(59.7%) of the respondents were females while 114(40.3%) were males. Set 2015/2016 had a frequency of 65, Set 2016/2017 had a frequency of 46, Set 2017/2018 had a frequency of 65, Set 2018/2019 had a frequency of 45, Set 2019/2020 had a frequency of 62.

Table 1.3: Marital Status

	Female (%)	Male (%)	Frequency (%)
Single	160(56.5)	114(40.3)	274(96.8)
Married	9(3.2)	0(0)	9(3.2)
TOTAL	169(59.7)	114(40.3)	283(100)

Table 1.3 shows that Single females were 160(56.5%), Married females were 9(3.2%), Single males were 114(40.3%), Married males were 0(0%). In total 274 (96.8%) of the respondents were single and 9(3.2%) of the respondents were married.

4.2 KNOWLEDGE OF HYPERTENSION AND HYPERTENSIVE RISK FACTORS

Figure 1.0

Table 2.0

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Good Knowledge	260	92
Bad Knowledge	23	8

Figure 1 and Table 2.0 above show the overall general knowledge of the respondents. 92% had an overall good knowledge whereas 8% had the wrong knowledge. The majority of the respondents had a good knowledge generally. Knowledge of hypertension and hypertensive risk factors was assessed by questions which were of the TRUE/FALSE type. Each variable was awarded a score of 1 for correct answers and 0 for wrong answers. In the case of optimal blood pressure of hypertensives, a score of 1 mark was awarded to 130/80, 0 marks 120/80, -1 90/60, -2 for 160/100. The minimum score was 0 and the

maximum score was 39. Using the cutoff of 77%, respondent who scored above this threshold (greater or equal 30) were considered to have good knowledge and those below this threshold (less than 30) were considered to have poor knowledge of Hypertension and its risk factors.

Table 2.1: Factors that contribute to Hypertension

Key: T – True F - False

	2015/2016		2016/2017		2017/2018		2018/2019		2019/2020		FREQUENCY(%)	
	T	F	T	F	T	F	T	F	T	F	T	F
DRUG	53	12	39	7	60	5	40	5	57	5	249(88)	34(12)
OLD AGE	62	3	41	5	62	3	44	1	60	2	269(95.1)	14(4.9)
STRESS	63	2	44	2	63	2	43	2	62	0	275(97.2)	8(2.9)
WITCHCRAFT	8	57	5	41	9	56	11	34	11	51	44(15.5)	239(84.5)
SMOKING	64	1	45	1	65	0	43	2	56	6	273(96.5)	10(3.5)
OBESITY	64	1	46	0	65	0	44	1	62	0	281(99.3)	2(0.7)
HIGH SALT INTAKE	62	3	45	1	65	0	44	1	62	0	278(98.2)	5(1.8)

Table 2.1 is a true/false frequency table of the factors that contribute to hypertension. 88% of the respondents acknowledged drugs as a factor that contributes to hypertension while 12% of them disagreed with that. 95.1% acknowledged Old age while 4.9% disagreed. 97.2% acknowledged stress while 2.9% disagreed. 15.5% acknowledged witchcraft while 84.5% disagreed. 96.5% acknowledged smoking while 3.5% disagreed. 99.3% acknowledged Obesity while 0.7% disagreed and 98.2% acknowledged high salt intake while 1.8% disagreed. Majority acknowledged Obesity as a contributing factor to hypertension.

Table 2.2: Secondary Causes of High Blood Pressure

Key: T – True F - False

	2015/2016		2016/2017		2017/2018		2018/2019		2019/2020		FREQUENCY (%)	
	T	F	T	F	T	F	T	F	T	F	T	F
Hyperthyroidism	62	3	45	1	62	3	37	8	56	6	262(92.6)	21(7.4)
Hyperaldosteronism	60	5	42	4	59	6	37	8	50	12	248(87.6)	35(12.4)
Kidney disease	64	1	45	1	62	3	37	8	48	14	256(90.5)	27(9.5)
Family History	47	18	30	16	49	16	34	11	56	6	216(76.3)	67(23.7)
Cushing Syndrome	63	2	44	2	55	10	36	9	51	11	249(88)	34(12)

Table 2.2 is a true/false frequency table showing the secondary causes of high blood pressure. 92.6% of the respondents acknowledged Hyperthyroidism as the secondary cause of hypertension while 7.4% disagreed. 87.6% acknowledged hyperaldosteronism while 12.4% disagreed. 90.5% acknowledged kidney disease while 9.5% disagreed. 76.3% acknowledged family history while 23.7% disagreed and 88% acknowledged Cushing's syndrome while 12% disagreed with that.

Table 2.3: Signs and Symptoms of High Blood Pressure**Key: T – True F - False**

	2015/2016		2016/2017		2017/2018		2018/2019		2019/2020		FREQUENCY (%)	
	T	F	T	F	T	F	T	F	T	F	T	F
Asymptomatic	59	6	44	2	60	5	40	5	42	20	245(86.6)	38(13.4)
Headache	64	1	45	1	63	2	42	3	56	6	270(95.4)	13(4.6)
Palpitations	61	4	46	0	62	3	39	6	57	5	265(93.6)	18(6.4)
Shortness of Breath	49	16	37	9	54	11	35	10	49	13	224(79.2)	59(20.8)
Visual Disturbances	62	3	44	2	65	0	37	8	46	16	254(89.8)	29(10.2)

Table 2.3 is a true/false frequency table showing the signs and symptoms of high blood pressure. 86.6% of the respondents said high blood pressure was asymptomatic while 13.4% disagreed with that. 95.4% acknowledged Headache as the major symptom of hypertension while 4.6% disagreed. 93.6% acknowledged palpitations while 6.4% disagreed. 79.2% acknowledged shortness of breath while 20.8% disagreed and 89.8% acknowledged visual disturbances while 10.2% disagreed with that.

Table 2.4: Factors that contribute to development of hypertension

	2015/2016		2016/2017		2017/2018		2018/2019		2019/2020		FREQUENCY (%)	
	T	F	T	F	T	F	T	F	T	F	T	F
Smoking	64	1	46	0	65	0	42	3	61	1	278(98.2)	5(1.8)
High LDL Cholesterol	60	5	41	5	58	7	38	7	59	3	256(90.5)	27(9.5)
Increasing Age	62	3	44	2	65	0	43	2	59	3	273(96.5)	10(3.5)
Stress	63	2	45	1	64	1	43	2	60	2	275(97.2)	8(2.8)
Family History	63	2	46	0	65	0	44	1	60	2	278(98.2)	5(1.8)
Chronic Renal Failure	63	2	46	0	61	4	40	5	53	9	263(92.9)	20(7.1)
Increased Fatty food	60	5	44	2	64	1	41	4	61	1	270(95.4)	13(4.6)
Increased use of salt	62	3	46	0	64	1	41	4	61	1	274(96.8)	9(3.2)
Sedentary Lifestyle	65	0	46	0	64	1	43	2	53	9	271(95.8)	12(4.2)
Oral Contraceptives	52	13	40	6	52	13	25	20	42	20	211(74.6)	72(25.4)

Table 2.4 is a true/false frequency table showing the factors that contribute to development of hypertension. 98.2% acknowledged smoking while 1.8% did not. 90.5% acknowledged High LDL cholesterol while 9.5% did not. 96.5% acknowledged Increasing age while 3.5% did not. 97.2% acknowledged stress while 2.8% did not. 98.2% acknowledged family history while 1.8% did not. 92.9% acknowledged chronic renal failure while 7.1% did not. 95.4% acknowledged increased fatty food while 4.6% did not. 96.8% acknowledged increased salt intake while 3.2% did not. 95.8% acknowledged sedentary lifestyle while 4.2% did not. 74.6% acknowledged oral contraceptives while 25.4% did not agree.

Table 2.5: Consequences of untreated High Blood pressure

	2015/2016		2016/2017		2017/2018		2018/2019		2019/2020		FREQUENCY(%)	
	T	F	T	F	T	F	T	F	T	F	T	F
Retinopathy	63	2	46	0	64	1	43	2	53	9	269(95.1)	14(4.9)
Stroke	65	0	46	0	65	0	42	3	60	2	278(98.2)	5(1.8)
Heart Failure	65	0	46	0	65	0	43	2	61	1	280(98.9)	3(1.1)
Kidney Failure	65	0	45	1	64	1	41	4	49	13	264(93.3)	19(6.7)
Coronary Artery Disease	60	5	44	2	60	5	42	3	59	3	265(93.6)	18(6.4)

Table 2.5 is a frequency table showing the consequences of untreated high blood pressure. 95.1% acknowledged retinopathy while 4.9% did not agree. 98.2% acknowledged stroke while 1.8% did not. 98.9% acknowledged heart failure while 1.1% did not. 93.3% acknowledged kidney failure while 6.7% did not. 93.6% acknowledged coronary artery disease while 6.4% did not agree.

Table 2.6: Goal Blood Pressure

	2015/2016	2016/2017	2017/2018	2018/2019	2019/2020	FREQUENCY (%)
120/80	29	20	29	31	30	139(49.1)
130/80	28	23	34	9	16	110(38.9)
160/100	8	3	2	4	15	32(11.3)
90/60	0	0	0	1	1	2(0.7)

Table 2.6 shows respondents' Ideal goal blood pressure in hypertensives. 49.1% of the respondents acknowledged 120/80 as the goal blood pressure. 38.9% acknowledged 130/80 as the goal blood pressure. 11.3% acknowledged 160/100 as the goal blood pressure while 0.7% acknowledged 90/60 as the goal blood pressure.

Table 2.7: Impact of Hypertension on Cardiovascular Disease

	2015/2016	2016/2017	2017/2018	2018/2019	2019/2020	FREQUENCY (%)
YES	65	46	65	45	61	282(99.6)
NO	0	0	0	0	1	1(0.4)

Table 2.7 seeks to find out if hypertension has an impact on cardiovascular disease. 99.6% of the respondents acknowledged that hypertension does have an impact on cardiovascular diseases while 0.4% disagree.

Table 2.8: Cardiovascular Diseases impacted upon by Hypertension

	2015/2016		2016/2017		2017/2018		2018/2019		2019/2020		FREQUENCY (%)	
	T	F	T	F	T	F	T	F	T	F	T	F
Myocardial infarction	59	6	38	8	57	8	37	8	51	10	242(8)	40(1)
Left ventricular hypertrophy	61	4	44	2	61	4	41	4	54	7	261	21
Heart Failure	64	1	46	0	62	3	42	3	56	5	270	12
Arrhythmias	56	9	38	8	56	9	32	13	49	12	231	51
Coronary Artery Disease	58	7	38	8	59	6	40	5	52	9	257	35

Table 2.8 is a true/false frequency table that identifies the cardiovascular diseases hypertension has an impact on. 242 respondents acknowledged Myocardial Infarction while 40 of them disagreed. 261 respondents acknowledged left ventricular hypertrophy while 21 of them disagreed. 270 respondents acknowledged heart failure while 12 of them disagreed. 231 respondents acknowledged arrhythmias while 51 of them disagreed and lastly 257 respondents acknowledged coronary artery disease while 35 of them disagreed to that.

4.3 ATTITUDE TOWARDS AVOIDANCE OF HYPERTENSION AND HYPERTENSIVE RISK FACTORS

Figure 2.0

Table 3.0

	Frequency	Percentage(%)
Positive Attitude	252	89
Negative Attitude	31	11

Figure 2 and Table 3.0 depicts the frequency and percentage of the attitude of medical students towards hypertension and its risk factors, 252 (89%) had a positive attitude and 31(11%) had a negative attitude.

Attitudes towards avoidance of hypertension and hypertensive risk factors was assessed using the 5-point Likert scale. The most correct variable was awarded a score of 5, while the next correct answer was awarded a score of 4, the neutral variable was awarded a score of 3. A wrong answer was awarded a score of 2. The most wrong answer was

awarded the score of 1. Maximum score in this section was 80 while the minimum is was. The cut off mark was at 80% meaning people that got below 64 marks were awarded bad attitudes and 64 marks and above were adjudged to have good attitudes.

Table 3.1: Should Know One's Blood Pressure

	2015/2016	2016/2017	2017/2018	2018/2019	2019/2020	FREQUENCY (%)
Strongly Agree	58	40	52	34	45	229(80.9)
Agree	4	5	11	10	14	44(15.5)
Neutral	1	0	0	0	0	1(0.4)
Disagree	0	1	0	0	0	1(0.4)
Strongly Disagree	2	0	2	1	3	8(2.8)

Table 3.1. This table depicts the attitude of medical students towards knowing their blood pressure 229 (80.9%) strongly agree, 44(15.5%) agree, 1(0.4%) are neutral, 1(0.4%) disagree, 8(2.8%) strongly disagree. Majority of the respondents strongly agree.

Table 3.2: Should Know One's Cholesterol Level

	2015/2016	2016/2017	2017/2018	2018/2019	2019/2020	FREQUENCY (%)
Strongly Agree	44	33	42	19	35	173(61.1)
Agree	15	11	21	21	21	89(13.4)
Neutral	4	2	0	4	4	14(4.9)
Disagree	0	0	0	0	0	0(0)
Strongly Disagree	2	0	2	1	2	7(2.5)

Table 3.2. This table depicts the attitude of medical students towards knowing their

cholesterol level 176 (61.1%) strongly agree, 89(13.4%) agree, 14(4.9%) are neutral, 0(0%) disagree, 7(2.5%) strongly disagree. Majority of the respondents strongly agree.

Table 3.3: Should Know One's Blood Sugar

	2015/2016	2016/2017	2017/2018	2018/2019	2019/2020	FREQUENCY (%)
Strongly Agree	52	33	47	27	46	205(72.4)
Agree	11	13	16	18	14	72(25.4)
Neutral	0	0	0	0	0	0(0)
Disagree	0	0	0	0	0	0(0)
Strongly Disagree	2	0	2	0	2	6(2.1)

Table 3.3. This table depicts the attitude of medical students towards knowing their blood sugar 205 (72.4%) strongly agree, 72(25.4%) agree, 0(0%) are neutral, 0(0%) disagree, 6(2.1%) strongly disagree. Majority of the respondents strongly agree.

Table 3.4: Belief That Hypertension Is Preventable

	2015/2016	2016/2017	2017/2018	2018/2019	2019/2020	FREQUENCY (%)
Strongly Agree	29	18	21	14	31	113(39.9)
Agree	23	16	27	21	25	112(39.6)
Neutral	9	9	17	9	6	50(17.7)
Disagree	2	3	0	1	0	6(2.1)
Strongly Disagree	2	0	0	0	0	2(0.7)

Table 3.4. This table depicts the attitude of medical students towards believing that hypertension is preventable 113 (39.9%) strongly agree, 112(39.6%) agree, 50(17.7%) are neutral, 6(2.1%) disagree, 2(0.7%) strongly disagree.

Table 3.5: Willingness To Exercise Regularly

	2015/2016	2016/2017	2017/2018	2018/2019	2019/2020	FREQUENCY (%)
Strongly Agree	24	15	15	11	20	85(30)
Agree	27	23	34	21	29	134(47.3)
Neutral	13	8	16	8	11	56(19.8)
Disagree	0	0	0	3	1	4(1.4)
Strongly Disagree	1	0	0	2	1	4(1.4)

Table 3.5. This table depicts the attitude of medical students and willingness 85 (30%) strongly agree, 134(47.3%) agree, 56(19.8%) are neutral, 4(1.4%) disagree, 4(1.4%) strongly disagree. Majority of the respondents agree.

Table 3.6: Willingness to Maintain A Healthy Lifestyle

	2015/2016	2016/2017	2017/2018	2018/2019	2019/2020	FREQUENCY (%)
Strongly Agree	38	14	25	14	30	121(42.8)
Agree	25	27	37	25	27	141(49.8)
Neutral	1	5	3	6	5	20(7.1)
Disagree	0	0	0	0	0	0(0)
Strongly Disagree	1	0	0	0	0	1(0.4)

Table 3.6. This table depicts the attitude of medical students towards maintaining a healthy lifestyle (42.8%) strongly agree, 141(49.8%) agree, 20(7.1%) are neutral, 0 (0%) disagree, 1(0.4%) strongly disagree. The majority of the respondents agree.

Table 3.7: Believe that People at High Risk of Hypertension Should Improve Their Lifestyle

	2015/2016	2016/2017	2017/2018	2018/2019	2019/2020	FREQUENCY (%)
Strongly Agree	56	35	51	28	50	220(77.7)
Agree	7	11	14	14	12	58(20.5)
Neutral	1	0	0	2	0	3(1.1)
Disagree	0	0	0	1	0	1(0.4)
Strongly Disagree	1	0	0	0	0	1(0.4)

Table 3.7. This table depicts the attitude of medical students towards knowing their blood pressure and if it helps improve their lifestyle if there's a high risk of hypertension 220 (77.7%) strongly agree, 58(20.5%) agree, 3(1.1%) are neutral, 1(0.4%) disagree, 1(0.4%) strongly disagree. Majority of the respondents strongly agree.

Table 3.8: Belief That Medications Are Necessary to Manage Hypertension

	2015/2016	2016/2017	2017/2018	2018/2019	2019/2020	FREQUENCY (%)
Strongly Agree	31	18	37	14	26	126(44.5)
Agree	25	23	25	20	27	120(42.4)
Neutral	6	5	2	9	7	29(10.2)
Disagree	2	0	1	2	2	7(2.5)
Strongly Disagree	1	0	0	0	0	1(0.4)

Table 3.8. This table depicts the attitude of medical students towards believing that medications are needed for the management of hypertension 126 (44.5%) strongly agree, 120(42.4%) agree, 29(10.2%) are neutral, 7(2.5%) disagree, 1(0.4%) strongly disagree.

Table 3.9: Belief That Reducing Salt Intake Helps Prevent Hypertension

	2015/2016	2016/2017	2017/2018	2018/2019	2019/2020	FREQUENCY (%)
Strongly Agree	35	20	31	11	26	123(43.5)
Agree	24	20	28	28	32	132(46.6)
Neutral	2	5	6	6	3	22(7.8)
Disagree	3	1	0	0	1	5(1.8)
Strongly Disagree	1	0	0	0	0	1(0.4)

Table 3.9. This table depicts the attitude of medical students towards believing that reduction of salt intake prevents hypertension 123 (43.5%) strongly agree, 132(46.6%) agree, 22(7.8%) are neutral, 5(1.8%) disagree, 1(0.4%) strongly disagree.

Table 3.10: Belief That Reducing Oil Intake Helps Prevent Hypertension

	2015/2016	2016/2017	2017/2018	2018/2019	2019/2020	FREQUENCY (%)
Strongly Agree	21	19	23	10	21	94(33.2)
Agree	28	22	30	28	32	140(49.5)
Neutral	10	5	11	6	7	39(13.8)
Disagree	5	0	1	1	2	9(3.2)
Strongly Disagree	1	0	0	0	0	1(0.4)

Table 3.10. This table depicts the attitude of medical students towards believing that reduction in intake of oil helps prevents hypertension 94 (33.2%) strongly agree, 140(49.5%) agree, 39(13.8%) are neutral, 9(3.2%) disagree, 1(0.4%) strongly disagree.

Table 3.11: Belief That Reducing/Quitting Smoking Helps Prevent Hypertension

	2015/2016	2016/2017	2017/2018	2018/2019	2019/2020	FREQUENCY (%)
Strongly Agree	48	27	36	18	31	160(56.5)
Agree	14	17	25	25	26	107(37.8)
Neutral	2	1	4	1	4	12(4.2)
Disagree	0	1	0	0	0	1(0.4)
Strongly Disagree	1	0	0	1	1	3(1.1)

Table 3.11. This table depicts the attitude of medical students towards believing that reduction/ quitting smoking helps prevent hypertension 160(56.5%) strongly agree, 107(37.8%) agree, 12(4.2%) are neutral, 1(0.4%) disagree, 3(1.1%) strongly disagree.

Table 3.12: Belief That Reducing Alcohol Intake Help Prevent Hypertension

	2015/2016	2016/2017	2017/2018	2018/2019	2019/2020	FREQUENCY (%)
Strongly Agree	44	24	33	16	30	147(51.9)
Agree	16	17	28	23	28	112(39.6)
Neutral	3	5	4	6	4	22(7.8)
Disagree	1	0	0	0	0	1(0.4)
Strongly Disagree	1	0	0	0	0	1(0.4)

Table 3.12. This table depicts the attitude of medical students towards believing that reduction of alcohol helps prevent hypertension 147(51.9%) strongly agree, 112(39.6%) agree, 22(7.8%) are neutral, 1(0.4%) disagree, 1(0.4%) strongly disagree.

Table 3.13: Belief That Reducing Psychological Stress Can Help Prevent Hypertension

	2015/2016	2016/2017	2017/2018	2018/2019	2019/2020	FREQUENCY (%)
Strongly Agree	36	18	25	19	32	130(45.9)
Agree	26	25	35	24	25	135(47.7)
Neutral	2	3	4	2	3	14(4.9)
Disagree	0	0	1	0	1	2(0.7)
Strongly Disagree	1	0	0	0	1	2(0.7)

Table 3.13. This table depicts the attitude of medical students towards believing that reduction of psychological stress helps prevents hypertension 130(45.9%) strongly agree, 135(47.7%) agree, 14(4.9%) are neutral, 2(0.7%) disagree, 2(0.7%) strongly disagree.

Table 3.14: Belief That Adequate Sleep Help Prevent Hypertension

	2015/2016	2016/2017	2017/2018	2018/2019	2019/2020	FREQUENCY (%)
Strongly Agree	33	18	20	19	22	112(39.6)
Agree	26	24	31	20	29	130(45.9)
Neutral	4	4	12	6	9	35(12.4)
Disagree	2	0	2	0	1	3(1.1)
Strongly Disagree	0	0	0	0	1	3(1.1)

Table 3.14. This table depicts the attitude of medical students towards believing that adequate sleep helps prevent hypertension 112(39.6%) strongly agree, 130(45.9%) agree, 35(12.4%) are neutral, 3(1.1%) disagree, 3(1.1%) strongly disagree.

Table 3.15: Belief That People At High Risk Of Hypertension Should Monitor Their Blood Pressure

	2015/2016	2016/2017	2017/2018	2018/2019	2019/2020	FREQUENCY (%)
Strongly Agree	57	36	46	32	49	220(77.7)
Agree	6	10	19	12	12	59(20.8)
Neutral	0	0	0	0	0	0(0)
Disagree	0	0	0	1	0	1(0.4)
Strongly Disagree	2	0	0	0	1	3(1.1)

Table 3.15. This table depicts the attitude of medical students towards believing that people at risk for hypertension should monitor their blood pressure 220(77.7%) strongly agree, 59(20.8%) agree, 0(0%) are neutral, 1(0.4%) disagree, 3(1.1%) strongly disagree

Table 3.16: Belief That Hypertension Is A Condition That Requires A Multidisciplinary Approach

	2015/2016	2016/2017	2017/2018	2018/2019	2019/2020	FREQUENCY (%)
Strongly Agree	49	24	33	22	37	165(58.3)
Agree	11	21	27	21	18	98(34.6)
Neutral	1	1	5	2	7	16(5.7)
Disagree	3	0	0	0	0	3(1.1)
Strongly Disagree	1	0	0	0	0	1(0.4)

Table 3.16 This table depicts the attitude of medical students towards believing that hypertension management requires a multidisciplinary approach 165(58.3%) strongly agree, 98(34.6%) agree, 16(5.7%) are neutral, 16(5.7%) disagree, 3(1.1%) strongly disagree.

4.4 PRACTICES THAT CONTRIBUTE TO AVOIDANCE OF HYPERTENSION AND HYPERTENSIVE RISK FACTORS

Figure 3

	Frequency	Percentage(%)
Good Practices	245	87
Bad Practices	38	13

Table 4.0

Figure 3 and Table 4.0 above show that 245 (87%) of the respondents were adjudged to have good practices, while 38(13%) were adjudged to have bad practices

In the assessment of practices that contribute to avoidance of hypertension and hypertensive risk factors. 3 marks were awarded for the most correct answer, 2 marks were awarded for a correct answer and 0 marks were awarded for a wrong answer. The cut off was 67%- 16 marks. Implying that persons with less than 16 marks were adjudged to exhibit Bad practices while persons with 16 marks and above were awarded Good practices

Table 4.1 Eat Fast Food

	2015/2016	2016/2017	2017/2018	2018/2019	2019/2020	FREQUENCY (%)
Frequently	9	10	14	8	10	51(18)
Sometimes	56	34	51	36	48	225(79.5)
Never	0	2	0	1	4	7(2.5)

Table 4.1 shows that a majority 79.5% of the respondents sometimes eat fast food, 18% of the respondents frequently eat fast food and 2.5% never eat fast food.

Table 4.2 Use More Than 3 Teaspoons Salt/Day

	2015/2016	2016/2017	2017/2018	2018/2019	2019/2020	FREQUENCY (%)
Frequently	9	4	4	1	4	22(7.8)
Sometimes	26	25	31	15	27	124(43.8)
Never	30	17	30	29	31	137(48.4)

Table 4.2 shows that that approximately half of the respondents 137(48.4%) do not use more than 3 teaspoons of salt per day, 124(43.8%) of the respondents sometimes use more than 3 teaspoons of salt, and 22(7.8%) frequently use more than 3 teaspoons of salt per day.

Table 4.3 Avoid Fatty Foods

	2015/2016	2016/2017	2017/2018	2018/2019	2019/2020	FREQUENCY (%)
Frequently	14	10	6	9	6	45(15.9)
Sometimes	46	32	52	30	49	209(73.9)
Never	5	4	7	6	7	29(10.2)

Table 4.3 shows that a majority 209(73.9%) of the respondents avoid the intake of fatty foods sometimes, 45 (15.9%) frequently avoid the intake of fatty foods, and 29(10.2) never avoid fatty foods intake.

Table 4.4 Try to Reduce Stress

	2015/2016	2016/2017	2017/2018	2018/2019	2019/2020	FREQUENCY (%)
Frequently	12	14	14	14	13	67(23.7)
Sometimes	53	28	42	26	42	191(67.5)
Never	0	4	9	5	7	25(8.8)

Table 4.4 shows that 191 (67.5%) of the respondents try to reduce stress sometimes, 67(23.7%) frequently reduce stress, and a meager 25(8.8%) never try to reduce stress they face.

Table 4.5 Avoid Smoking

	2015/2016	2016/2017	2017/2018	2018/2019	2019/2020	FREQUENCY (%)
Frequently	59	38	62	41	51	251(88.7)
Sometimes	3	7	2	2	4	18(6.4)
Never	3	1	1	2	7	14(4.9)

Table 4.5 shows that majority of the respondents 251(88.7%) frequently avoided smoking, 18(6.4%) sometimes avoided smoking, and a paltry 14(4.9%) never avoided smoking

Table 4.6 Control Your Body Weight

	2015/2016	2016/2017	2017/2018	2018/2019	2019/2020	FREQUENCY (%)
Frequently	35	20	26	24	28	133(47.0)
Sometimes	21	18	29	14	25	107(37.8)
Never	9	8	10	7	9	43(15.2)

Table 4.6 shows that 133(47%) of the respondents frequently controlled their body weight, 107(37.8%) sometimes controlled their body weight, and 43(15.2%) never controlled their body weight.

Table 4.7 Engage In Physical Activity

	2015/2016	2016/2017	2017/2018	2018/2019	2019/2020	FREQUENCY (%)
Frequently	31	20	27	17	19	114(40.3)
Sometimes	34	21	38	25	41	159(56.2)
Never	0	5	0	3	2	10(3.5)

Table 4.7 shows that 159(56.2%) of the respondents sometimes engaged in physical activity, 114(40.3%) frequently engaged in physical activity, while a minority 10(3.5%) never engaged in physical activity.

Table 4.8 Monitor their Blood Pressure levels

	2015/2016	2016/2017	2017/2018	2018/2019	2019/2020	FREQUENCY (%)
Frequently	7	4	11	4	5	31(11)
Sometimes	47	35	41	26	40	189(66.7)
Never	11	7	13	15	17	63(22.3)

Table 4.8 shows that a majority 189 (66.7%) of the respondents sometimes monitor their blood pressure, 63(22.3%) never monitor their blood pressure, and 31 (11%) frequently measure their blood pressure levels.

4.5 ASSOCIATION BETWEEN KNOWLEDGE OF AND PRACTICES TO CURB HYPERTENSION AND ITS RISK FACTORS

Decision Rule for assessing if the test is significant (for $z=0.05$)

If $p < \text{or} = 0.05$, the test is significant (There is a significant relationship between two variables)

If $p > 0.05$, the test is not significant (there is no significant relationship between two variables)

A correlation coefficient of 0.10-0.30 will be used as an indicator for a negligible positive association

A correlation coefficient of 0.30-0.50 will be used as an indicator for weak or low positive association

A correlation coefficient of 0.50 and above will be used as an indicator to represent a strong positive correlation

A correlation coefficient less than 0 or negative value indicates that there is an inverse relationship between the two variables

Table 5.1

VARIABLE	CORRELATION COEFFICIENT	P-Value*
Good knowledge - Good practices	0.890	0.043
Good knowledge - Bad practices	0.339	0.577
Bad knowledge - Good practices	0.233	0.706
Bad knowledge - Bad practices	-0.267	0.664

Statistically significant at $p < 0.05$

Table 5.1 shows the association between knowledge and practices of medical students to the risk factors of hypertension, there is a significant positive relationship between good knowledge and good practices, $r(3) = 0.890$, $p = 0.043$ which is less than value 0.05, there is no significant positive relationship between good knowledge and bad practices, having a positive coefficient of 0.339 and p value of 0.577 which is above our reference of 0.05, there is also no significant relationship between bad knowledge and good practices, with a coefficient of 0.233 and p value of 0.706, between bad knowledge and bad practices, there was a negative correlation with -0.267 and a p value which is above the reference point

CHAPTER 5

DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC

In this study, Table 1.0 revealed that among the respondents, the age range was between 19-36 years of age and the most responses came from people between the ages 22-24; age 23 had the highest responses with 21.8% coming from the age group and the least responses came from age 36 with 0.4% of responses. Table 1.1 which indicated the sexes of the respondents showed that out of the total respondents, 59.7% were females with the most responses coming from set 2017/2018 having about 24.2% of respondents, while the least responses came from set 2016/2017 with a percentage of 15.3, The males made up 40.3 percent of respondents, the most responses coming from set 2015/2016 with 28.1% of male respondents while set 2018/2019 had the least of respondents making up 11.5 %, Table 1.2 shows the marital status of the respondents, most of the target population were single, making up about 96.8%, with 58.4% making up females and 41.6% making up the male population of the single respondents while 3.2% were married with 100% of the married respondents being females

5.2 KNOWLEDGE OF HYPERTENSION AND ITS RISK FACTORS AMONG CLINICAL MEDICAL STUDENTS IN BINGHAM UNIVERSITY TEACHING HOSPITAL

Knowledge of hypertension and its risk factors among medical students is of utmost public health importance, proper practices on preventing hypertension risk factors and hypertension management are only possible with adequate knowledge regarding such practices.

A cross-sectional survey was conducted by Mohammed Hisam, Asma Nour and Shayoub M in 2018 on "Assessment of Knowledge about Hypertension among students of the first year in medical colleges, in International University of Africa (IUA)" (18). The overall knowledge of students was found to be 62.97% and this is in keeping with our findings

which revealed that amongst the 552 respondents that we had, 92% of them were well informed on hypertension and its risk factors whereas only 8% of them had the wrong knowledge on hypertension and its risk factors.

Concerning the secondary causes of high blood pressure, 92.6% of the respondents agreed with hyperaldosteronism followed by kidney disease with 90.5% whereas about 23.7% disagreed with family history as a secondary cause of high blood pressure. Signs and symptoms of hypertension from top to bottom according to the respondents were; Headache 95.4%, palpitations 93.6%, visual disturbances 89.8%, asymptomatic 86.6%, shortness of breath 79.2%.

When asked further on the factors contributing to the development of hypertension, the majority of the respondents agreed with smoking and family history both at 98.2% followed by stress at 97.2%, increased use of salt at 96.8%, increasing age at 96.5%, sedentary lifestyle 95.8%, increased fatty foods 95.4%, chronic renal failure 92.9%, high LDL cholesterol 90.5%, oral contraceptives 74.6% accordingly which is not similar to a descriptive cross-sectional conducted by Pugie Tawanda Chimberengwal and Mergan Naidoo (17), on behalf of the cooperative inquiry group Discipline of Public Health Medicine, School of Nursing and Public Health, University of KwaZulu-Natal, Durban, South Africa in 2019. The study was on "Knowledge, attitudes and practices related to hypertension among residents of a disadvantaged rural community; Matebele land in southern Zimbabwe. 304 respondents were enrolled in the study (mean age, 59 years), and a majority were women (65.4%). Knowledge of hypertension was poor, with 64.8% of respondents stating that stress was its main cause, 85.9% stating that palpitations were a symptom of hypertension and 59.8% of respondents added salt on the table. The more education respondents received, the more likely they were knowledgeable about hypertension. Poor knowledge was associated with a lack of education and strong beliefs in herbal and traditional medicines in the community, which influenced attitudes and practices on hypertension. Dietary risk factors were linked to poor knowledge.

When asked on the consequences of untreated high blood pressure, a majority of the respondents agreed to heart failure 98.9% and stroke 98.3%, followed by retinopathy

95.1%, coronary artery disease 93.6%, kidney failure 93.3%.

The goal blood pressure according to a larger percentage of the respondents 49.1% was 120/80mmHg however 38.9% agreed with 130/80mmHg. 99.6% of the respondents when asked acknowledged that hypertension does have an impact on cardiovascular diseases only 0.4% said otherwise. To further assess the knowledge of the respondents on the impact of hypertension on some cardiovascular diseases, 270 of the respondents said hypertension had a higher impact on heart failure, 261 respondents agreed with left ventricular hypertrophy, 257 of them agreed with coronary artery disease, 242 respondents agreed with myocardial infarction and lastly, 231 respondents agreed with Arrhythmias.

A descriptive cross-sectional study was accomplished by Mukhtiar Baig et al, at Jeddah, Saudi Arabia, in 2014 titled “Prevalence of obesity and hypertension among University students’ and their knowledge and attitude towards risk factors of cardiovascular disease (CVD) in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia”. The aim of the study was to investigate the prevalence of obesity and hypertension among University students. They recommended that a large-scale awareness program should be initiated from health ministry on the electronic and print media.

5.3 ATTITUDE TOWARDS AVOIDANCE OF HYPERTENSION AND HYPERTENSIVE RISK FACTORS

The results of the attitude survey offer insightful information about how medical students feel about hypertension and its risk factors. Overall, 89% of medical students show a positive attitude regarding hypertension, whereas only 11% indicate a negative attitude toward the condition.

Cross-sectional descriptive research was undertaken among undergraduate medical students in the Andhra Pradesh district of Guntur. 336 students took part in the study. After analysis, the findings are as follows: According to the current study, knowledge of hypertension and the risk factors that contribute to it is growing over time. The final years were shown to have the highest percentage of positive attitudes (99.3%) toward risk

factors for hypertension. Both surveys revealed that the majority of medical students have positive attitudes, even though they had a higher percentage of them (21). In terms of knowledge, the results show that a significant proportion of medical students strongly agree that they should know their blood pressure (80.9%), cholesterol level (61.1%), and blood sugar level (72.4%). This indicates that the students recognize the importance of monitoring these health indicators in relation to hypertension. It also suggests that they have a proactive attitude towards their own health and are willing to take responsibility for monitoring their health parameters.

Additionally, the majority of students (39.9% strongly agree, 39.6% agree) believe that hypertension can be prevented. This implies that they believe there is a chance that lifestyle changes and preventative measures can lower the risk of hypertension. This proactive approach to prevention is crucial because it shows a readiness to encourage healthy habits and inform patients of the value of preventative actions.

Students who are willing to make lifestyle changes include exercising frequently (30% strongly agree, 47.3% agree) and maintaining a healthy weight, lifestyle (49.8% agree, 42.8% strongly agree). This displays their readiness to develop wholesome habits to stop or control hypertension. It also suggests a favorable outlook on modifying one's lifestyle to control hypertension. In a cross-sectional descriptive study conducted among undergraduate medical students of Guntur district, Andhra Pradesh. In the study, 336 students participated. The results were analyzed and they are as follows: in the present study, more than 90% of the study population included fruits in their diet. The habit of junk food eating is found to be around 50%. Only 47% of the study population are doing adequate physical exercise and walking is found to be the common physical activity. Harmful habits like tobacco use, alcohol intake and high salt intake are found to be very low in the present Study. Knowledge and attitude of medical students of various semesters are good towards risk factors of hypertension but the warning signs are about half of study participants are not doing regular physical exercise & consuming junk food & some of them are having habits of alcohol, smoking which are modifiable risk factors

that leads to hypertension at very early age. (21)

According to these two studies, only a small percentage of medical students actually adhere to healthy eating habits. This may be because of a variety of reasons, including stress from lectures, late-night reading and snacking, a lack of time to prepare wholesome meals, and for some, a lack of sufficient funds.

Furthermore, a sizable portion of students (77.7%) strongly concur that those who are at high risk of hypertension should alter their lifestyle. This shows that they are aware of the need for lifestyle modifications in treating hypertension and that they have a positive outlook on helping those who are at high risk.

In terms of medication use, a significant portion of students (44.5% strongly agree, 42.4% agree) believe that drugs are essential for managing hypertension. This demonstrates their understanding of the significance of pharmacological therapies in blood pressure regulation. It also shows a favorable viewpoint on the administration of drugs to treat hypertension.

In terms of salt intake, the results reveal that a considerable number of students strongly agree or agree that reducing salt intake (43.5% strongly agree, 46.6% agree) and reducing oil intake (33.2% strongly agree, 49.5% agree) help prevent hypertension. This reflects their knowledge of the dietary factors that contribute to hypertension and the importance of making dietary changes. It also indicates a positive attitude towards dietary modifications as a means of preventing hypertension.

The majority of medical students (56.5%) strongly concur, as shown in Table 3.11, that cutting back on or quitting smoking helps reduce hypertension. Another 37.8% share this viewpoint. Indicating that the majority of medical students are aware of the connection between smoking and hypertension and favor quitting as a preventative treatment for hypertension, just a very tiny fraction (0.4%) disagree or strongly disagree.

According to Table 3.12, 51.9% of medical students strongly agree that limiting alcohol use helps prevent hypertension, while 39.6% do as well. Once more, only a tiny fraction (0.4%) strongly disagree or disagree. This implies that the majority of medical students

are aware of the link between drinking and hypertension and are in favor of cutting back as a preventative approach.

According to Table 3.13, a sizable majority of medical students (45.9%) strongly believe that lowering psychological stress can aid in the prevention of hypertension, and another 47.7% concur. Only 0.7% strongly disagree or disagree with the statement. This shows that the majority of medical students are aware of how stress affects blood pressure and are in favor of stress reduction as a preventative intervention.

In Table 3.14, a substantial number of medical students (39.6%) strongly agree that adequate sleep helps prevent hypertension, and 45.9% agree with this belief. Some students (12.4%) remain neutral, possibly indicating a need for further education or clarification. Only a small percentage (1.1%) disagree or strongly disagree, suggesting that the majority of medical students understand the importance of adequate sleep in maintaining blood pressure and support it as a preventive measure for hypertension.

Table 3.15 shows that a large majority of medical students (77.7%) strongly agree that people at high risk of hypertension should monitor their blood pressure, and 20.8% agree with this belief. Only a small percentage (0.4%) disagree or strongly disagree. This suggests that the majority of medical students understand the significance of blood pressure monitoring for high-risk individuals and support it as a preventive measure for hypertension.

Lastly, in Table 3.16, a significant proportion of medical students (58.3%) strongly agree that hypertension management requires a multidisciplinary approach, and 34.6% agree with this belief. Some students (5.7%) remain neutral, possibly indicating a need for further understanding or exposure to the multidisciplinary nature of hypertension management. Only a small percentage (1.1%) disagree or strongly disagree, suggesting that the majority of medical students acknowledge the importance of a multidisciplinary approach in effectively managing hypertension.

Overall, the survey results suggest that medical students have a positive attitude towards hypertension and its risk factors. They recognize the importance of knowledge, lifestyle modifications, and medications in preventing and managing hypertension.

They recognize the importance of smoking cessation, reducing alcohol intake, reducing psychological stress, ensuring adequate sleep, blood pressure monitoring for high-risk individuals, and a multidisciplinary approach in hypertension management. These positive attitudes are crucial in promoting preventive measures and effective management of hypertension in their future practice as healthcare professionals. These findings are promising as they indicate that future healthcare professionals are well-informed and committed to promoting hypertension prevention and control. This positive attitude towards hypertension and its risk factors is essential for effective patient education and management in the future.

5.4 PRACTICES THAT CONTRIBUTE TO AVOIDANCE OF HYPERTENSION AND HYPERTENSIVE RISK FACTORS

From Figure 3 and Table 4.0, which were results obtained from the 283 respondents in this research, it showed that a majority 87% exhibited good practices while just 13% exhibited bad practices. This is a sharp contrast with the 2014 cross-sectional study by Mukhtair Baig et al in Saudi Arabia (22) which observed sub-optimal practices towards prevention of hypertension at 20%. This was noticed amongst university students in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia. The reason for this disparity in “Good Practices” could be solely attributed to the demographic of study which were clinical students. Compared to other non- medical oriented university students, these clinical students have shown to exhibit better Practices. The results from Mukhtair Baig et al (22) was also in keeping with another study by Marc Machaalani et al (24) in which just 21.93% of the respondents of that study showed adequate practices. Comparing these studies, our research study has a wholly different point of view which as said earlier is largely due to the highly health-educated demographic involved in this study.

Table 4.1 shows that 18% of the respondents frequently ate fast food, while a majority

79.5% sometimes ate fast food, a minute 2.5% of the respondents never ate fast food. It is quite evident that the high number of persons that frequently and sometimes eat fast foods is most likely a result of culminating work load and stress faced by these students. Their last resorts is usually these fast foods that can be gotten off the streets and via deliveries.

Table 4.2 showed that 7.8% of the respondents used more than 3 teaspoons of salt/day frequently, 43.8% sometimes used more than 3 teaspoons of salt/day, while 48.4 % of the respondents never used more than 3 teaspoon of salt/ day. This result correlate positively with Mukhtair Baig et al cross-sectional study (22) which found out that 32.5% of the university students who served as respondents used more than 3 teaspoon of salt/day. Our study results contrasts with that of Marc Maachalani et al study (24) which showed that 44.8 % of the respondents which were hypertensive patient controlled their salt intake. Marc Maachalani et al study was also corroborated by a Nigerian study by Jennifer Anyanti et al which found out that 54.6% minimized their salt intake. While the salt intake may not be objectively quantified due to non-use of appropriate measures while cooking instead, indiscriminate adding of spices according to one's preferred taste is usually practiced. Also, the amount of salt used in foods eaten out of home i.e. fast foods cannot be objectively quantified

Table 4.3 shows that 15.9% of the respondents frequently avoided fatty foods, 73.9% sometimes avoided fatty foods, while 10.2% never avoided fatty foods. This shows that majority of the respondents do not shy from eating fatty foods although majority do it in moderation. The result from this study avers with results from Mukhtair Baig et al study(22) in which it was found that 13% avoided fatty foods. The similarity between these two studies is due to the fact that the demographics of study are university students. Hence, similar results were obtained. Jennifer Anyanti et al's study (26) observed that 32.5% of the respondents reduced fatty food intake. The fact that it was just a mere minority of the respondents that observed reduced fatty food intake, corroborates the results of our research study. In a cross sectional survey by Dan Gong et al(25) amongst community dwellers in china, 38.1% balanced intake of meat a source of fats with

vegetables. This alludes a conscious effort by the respondents to reduce fatty food intake, also supporting the results of our research study.

Table 4.4 shows that 23.7% of the respondents frequently tried to reduce stress, a majority 67% sometimes tried to reduce stress, while 8.8% never tried to relieve their stress levels. In Dan Gong et al (25) cross-sectional study it was found out that a majority 89.4% of the respondents had low work stress levels which is quite laudable and in keeping with our results which found that a majority 67% sometimes tried to relieve stress levels. Our results is in contrast with the cross-sectional study by Mukhtair Baig et al (22) which showed that just a minute 6.4% tried to reduce stress. In the Nigerian study by Jennifer Anyanti et al (26), it was observed that just 4.2% avoided anxiety. This is quite poor as it invariably leads to in an increase in stress levels causing increased blood pressure levels. Table 4.5 observed that 88.7% frequently avoided smoking, 6.4% sometimes avoided smoking, 4.9% never avoided smoking. This research result confers with that of Dan gong et al study (25) which revealed that 72.5% of the respondents did not smoke. Our results of the respondents that never avoided smoking which was put at 4.9% which corresponds to a minority of the respondents avers with that of Takele Tadesse et al study (23) which found that just 2.6% smoked cigarettes. Munde Linda et al (29) in another cross-sectional study in 2007 identified people that smoked as 9.54% which also corroborates to our minority smokers. In a major contrast with that our results in Table 4.5, a cross-sectional study by Mukhtair Baig et al (22) discovered that just 13.4% avoided smoking, implying that the indulgent smokers were in the majority. Jennifer Anyanti et al (26) in a cross-sectional study in 2020 also identified 13.5% of the respondents that avoided smoking, also implying that the smokers made up most of the respondents of that study.

Table 4.6% identified persons that frequently controlled their body weight as 47%, sometimes controlled their body weight as 37.8%, never controlled their body weight as 15.2%. results from our study concurs with the study by Dan Gong et al (25) amongst China community dwellers which found that 48.8% controlled their body weight. Why the results from our study and the Chinese study concur is solely because of how highly

educated these clinical students that served as our study population are and the caste system in Asian countries in which being overweight and obese if faced with stigma. Hence, we have similar results from the comparison of our study and the Asian study. In another study by Mukhtair Baig et al (22) only about 11.3% tried to maintain normal body weight which is quite poor compared to findings from our own study.

Table 4.7% shows that 40.3% of the respondents frequently engage in physical activity, 56.2% sometimes engaged in physical activity and just 3.5% never engaged in physical activity. The results concur with that of Dan Gong et al ((25) in which a minority 30.9% frequently performed physical activity. It also avers with results from Munde Linda et al (19) and Jennifer Anyanti et al (26) respectively which 73.05% and 57.5% respectively were said to perform physical exercises.

Table 4.8 shows 11% of the respondents frequently monitor their blood pressure, 66.7% sometimes monitored their blood pressure while 22.3% never monitor their blood pressure levels. In contrast with Dan Gong et al (25) cross sectional study from which results obtained showed that a majority 76.9% monitored their blood pressure regularly, it is clear that these clinical medical students do not frequently monitor their blood pressure. This could be alluded to the fact that there might be belief that at these young age less than 30 years, there will be no cases of hypertension. This is becoming a fallacy as hypertension in the younger demographic seems to be on the rise.

5.5 ASSOCIATION BETWEEN KNOWLEDGE AND PRACTICES

This study (Table5.1) indicated that there was a significant positive association between good knowledge and good practices, ($p=0.043$), which showed that a good knowledge on the risk factors of hypertension would most likely be associated with good practices towards prevention of the risk factors, and there was a strong positive correlation coefficient (0.890), which is an indicator that an increase in good knowledge would lead to an increase in practices,

In the association between good knowledge and bad practices, the study showed no significant positive association as the p value (0.577) was above 0.05, showing that

theoretically it cannot be proven that a person can have bad practices while also having good knowledge, the correlation coefficient for the association between good knowledge and bad practices was ($r=0.339$) showing that there was a weak positive association between good knowledge and bad practices

The study between bad knowledge and good practices showed that there was no significance in the association as the p value was 0.706 which was above 0.05 and having a correlation coefficient of 0.233 which is negligible

In the association between bad knowledge and bad practices there was also no significant association with p value of 0.664, however there was a negative correlation coefficient of -0.267, showing that in the study conducted there was an inverse relationship between bad knowledge and bad practices which is not in support of the study carried out by Mukhiar Baig in 2014, aimed to identify the “Prevalence of obesity and hypertension among university students’ and their knowledge and attitude towards risk factors of cardiovascular diseases established an association between knowledge of and practices regarding avoidance of hypertensive risk factors. The study showed that students with poor knowledge were likely to exhibit poor avoidance practices. (22)

5.6 CONCLUSION

This study on the knowledge, attitude and practices towards hypertension and its risk factors revealed that 92% of respondents had a good knowledge on hypertension and its risk factors, 89% had a good attitude towards hypertension and hypertensive risk factors, while 87% had good practices towards the avoidance of risk factors that predisposes to hypertension, In the association between the knowledge of hypertension and practices to avoid hypertensive risk factors, it was found that there was a significant positive association between good knowledge and good practices ($p=0.043$) and a strongly positive correlation (correlation coefficient= 0.890) showing that good knowledge would most likely be associated with good practices, there was also a negative correlation coefficient between bad knowledge and bad practices, (correlation coefficient = -0.267) which showed an inverse relationship between bad knowledge and bad practices, so it

can be said that from this study, most of the students have a good knowledge, attitude and practices, and there is a strong positive association between good knowledge and good practices

5.7 RECOMMENDATION

1. Government: Federal and State governments through the Federal Ministry of Health and State's Ministry of Health should organize large scale awareness programs on Hypertension, detailing predisposing factors, necessary preventive practices in order for the Nigerian citizens particularly the youths aged 19-24 to have an expounded knowledge of, positive attitude and good practices towards avoidance of hypertension.
2. University: Nigerian Medical schools should develop and implement mandatory health education programs that will be tailored to fill in the gaps in knowledge, practice and attitudes towards Hypertension. These programs can be integrated into the curriculum or conducted as workshops. These programs will be based on evidence based medicine and appropriately curated for the youths. Also, universities could organize free health check-ups for their students of whom most are youths.
3. Students: Medical students should be educated on various diets that predisposes them to hypertension.. Also, the students are also encouraged to be involved actively in physical exercises weekly so as to lower the risk factors for the development of hypertension.

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APPENDIX 1
QUESTIONNAIRE

Section A Consent

We are final year medical students of the College of Health Sciences in Bingham University, Karu, Nasarawa State, Nigeria, and for academic purpose we are conducting a research titled " **Knowledge, Attitude and Practices of Hypertension and its risk factors among Clinical Medical Students in Bingham University Teaching Hospital,** " We will appreciate your consent to answering the questions contained in this questionnaire

CONFIDENTIALITY

All answers you will provide here will be confidential and will be used only for the purpose of this study

RISKS

No invasive procedures or tissue samples will be obtained from you as part of the study

VOLUNTARISM

Your participation is voluntary and will in no way affect you, should you turn down this request being made to you to participate

COMPENSATION

No compensation will be offered for participation in this study.

Do you agree to participate in this research? If yes, tick

If agreed, participant's signature:.....

Section B: Socio-Demographic Information

1. Age in years (age at last birthday):
2. Sex Male Female
3. Marital Status: Single Married
- 4 Ethnic Group:

5. Religion: Christianity [] Islam []

6. Present Class: 400Level [] 500level [] 600level []

7. Place of Residence (where you stay when in school): Hostel on campus []

Hostel off campus []

SECTION C: KNOWLEDGE

The following factors contribute to the causes of high blood pressure, For each statement tick[✓]whether it is true or false.

1.

	CAUSES	TRUE	FALSE
	Drug		
	Old age		
	Stress		
	Witch craft		
	Smoking		
	Obesity		
	High salt intake		

2. The following are secondary causes of high blood pressure, For each statement tick[✓]whether it is true or false.

	SECONDARY CAUSES OF HYPERTENSION	TRUE	FALSE
	Hyperthyroidism		
	Hyperaldosteronism		
	Kidney disease		
	Family history		
	Cushing syndrome		

3. The following are signs and symptoms of high blood pressure, For each statement tick[✓]whether it is true or false.

	SYMPTOMS	TRUE	FALSE
	Asymptomatic		
	Headache		
	Palpitations		
	Shortness of breath		
	Visual disturbances		

4 The following factors contribute to development of hypertension For each statement tick[✓]whether it is true or false.

	FACTORS	TRUE	FALSE
	Smoking		
	Obesity		
	High LDL cholesterol		
	Increasing age (>55years)		
	Stress		
	Family history of heart disease		
	Chronic renal failure		

	Increased fatty food intake		
	Increased use of salt		
	Sedentary lifestyle		
	Oral contraceptives		

5. The following are the consequences of untreated high blood pressure For each statement tick[✓]whether it is true or false.

	CONSEQUENCES	YES	NO
	Retinopathy		
	Stroke		
	Heart failure		
	Kidney failure		
	Coronary artery disease		

6. What is the goal blood pressure for patients with hypertension For each statement tick[✓]whether it is true or false

	GOAL BLOOD PRESSURE (mmHg)	TRUE	FALSE
	130/80		
	90/60		
	120/80		
	160/100		

7. Does hypertension have any impact on Cardiovascular diseases YES []
 NO []

8. If yes which of the following cardiovascular diseases do you think it has impacts on For each statement tick[✓]whether it is true or false.

	CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES	TRUE	FALSE
	Myocardial infarction		
	Left ventricular hypertrophy		
	Heart failure		
	Arrhythmia		
	Coronary artery disease		

SECTION D ATTITUDE

1. Should one know one's blood pressure level

Strongly Disagree[] Disagree[] Neutral[] Agree [] Strongly Agree []

2. Should one know cholesterol level

Strongly Disagree[] Disagree[] Neutral[] Agree [] Strongly Agree []

3. Should one know blood sugar level

Strongly Disagree[] Disagree[] Neutral[] Agree [] Strongly Agree []

4. Do you believe that hypertension is preventable

Strongly Disagree[] Disagree[] Neutral[] Agree [] Strongly Agree []

5. Are you willing to exercise regularly
- Strongly Disagree[] Disagree[] Neutral[] Agree [] Strongly Agree []
6. Are you willing to maintain a healthy lifestyle
- Strongly Disagree[] Disagree[] Neutral[] Agree [] Strongly Agree []
7. Do you believe that people at high risk for hypertension should improve their lifestyle
- Strongly Disagree[] Disagree[] Neutral[] Agree [] Strongly Agree []
8. Do you believe that medications are necessary to manage hypertension
- Strongly Disagree[] Disagree[] Neutral[] Agree [] Strongly Agree []
9. Do you believe that reducing salt intake help prevent hypertension
- Strongly Disagree[] Disagree[] Neutral[] Agree [] Strongly Agree []
10. Do you believe that reducing oil intake help prevent hypertension
- Strongly Disagree[] Disagree[] Neutral[] Agree [] Strongly Agree []
11. Do you believe that quitting smoking help prevent hypertension
- Strongly Disagree[] Disagree[] Neutral[] Agree [] Strongly Agree []
12. Do you believe that reducing alcohol intake help prevent hypertension
- Strongly Disagree[] Disagree[] Neutral[] Agree [] Strongly Agree []
13. Do you believe that reducing psychological stress can help prevent hypertension
- Strongly Disagree[] Disagree[] Neutral[] Agree [] Strongly Agree []
14. Do you believe that adequate sleep help prevent hypertension
- Strongly Disagree[] Disagree[] Neutral[] Agree [] Strongly Agree []

15. Do you believe that people at high risk for hypertension should monitor their BP

Strongly Disagree[] Disagree[] Neutral[] Agree [] Strongly Agree []

16. Do you believe that hypertension is a condition that requires a multidisciplinary approach

Strongly Disagree[] Disagree[] Neutral[] Agree [] Strongly Agree []

SECTION E Practices

17. Do you eat fast food

Frequently[] Sometimes[] Never []

18. Do you use more than 3 teaspoon salt/day

Frequently[] Sometimes[] Never []

19. Do you avoid fatty foods

Frequently[] Sometimes[] Never []

20. Do you try to reduce stress

Frequently[] Sometimes[] Never []

21. Do you avoid smoking

Frequently[] Sometimes[] Never []

22. Do you try to control your body weight

Frequently[] Sometimes[] Never []

23. Do you engage in physical activity

Frequently[] Sometimes[] Never []

24. Do you Monitor your BP

Frequently [] Sometimes[] Never []